

Research

Impact of Air Pollution from Factories and Vehicles on Patients with Lung Cancer Disease and COPD:Nepal

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Abstract: The effect of air pollution on humans is a worrisome factor that has gained prominence over the years due to the importance of the topic to society. Lung cancer and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are among the diseases associated with pollution that increase the mortality rate in Nepal and worldwide. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the impacts of air pollutants on mortality rates from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and lung cancer (LC) using vector autoregressive (VAR) modeling. The adjusted model was a VAR (1) and, according to the Granger causality test, the air pollutants selected were PM₁₀, O₃, CO, NO₂, and SO₂. The shocks applied to the variables O₃, using the impulse response function, negatively impacted COPD; in the eighth period, which is stabilized. The LC variable suffered more significant variations from O₃ and after a shock in this variable, an initially negative response in LC occurred and the series stabilized in period nine. After one year, 20.19% of COPD variance was explained by O₃. After twelve months, the atmospheric pollutant O₃ represented 5.00% and NO₂ represented 4.02% of LC variance. Moreover, the variables that caused the highest impact on COPD and LC mortality rates were O₃ and NO₂, indicating that air pollution influences the clinical state of people who have these diseases and even contributes to their development. The VAR model was able to identify the air pollutants that have the most significant impact on the diseases analyzed and explained the interrelationship between them.

Keywords: air pollution, lung cancer, COPD

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Introduction

Kathmandu Valley used to be famous for its temples, but now it is known for its high levels of pollution. The city that is known for its temples is now covered in dust and smoke. The beautiful blue hills and clear blue sky that used to be seen in the valley almost twenty years ago now look dull and unclear because of the trapped pollution that hangs above them[1]. In 2011, according to the Central Bureau of Statistics, Kathmandu had a population density of 13,225 people per square kilometer. The population of Kathmandu was also growing at a rate of 4.78% [2]. The valley has a lot of people because it is the capital city and people from all over the country come to the city for a better life and opportunities. The valley is in the middle of tall mountains that are between 2000 and 2800 meters above sea level [3,4]. Because of this, the valley has a special shape like a bowl where the wind doesn't move much, so the pollutants in the

air stay trapped there. This means that the valley is easily affected by air pollution. World Health Organization (WHO) defines air pollution as contamination of the indoor or outdoor environment by any chemical, physical, or biological agent that modifies the natural characteristics of the atmosphere [5,6]. Common sources of air pollution are household combustion devices, motor vehicles, industrial facilities, and forest fires [7]. Air pollution is a complex mixture of thousands of components, majority of which include airborne Particulate Matter (PM) and gaseous pollutants like ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), volatile organic compounds (like benzene), carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), etc. [8, 9]. A variety of respiratory and other diseases, which can also be fatal, are caused by outdoor and indoor air pollution [7]. Particulate Matter (PM 10) is that suspended particle that is about 10µm in diameter and mainly arises from the poor quality roads, construction sites, and farms and is responsible for causing irritation in eyes, nose, and acute respiratory infections [10]. High rate of PM10 associated mortality and respiratory illness are found in children and adults [11]. On the other hand PM2.5 (particles less than 2.5 µm in diameter) penetrate deep into the lung, irritate and corrode the alveolar wall, consequently impair lung function [12], and even penetrate the blood [7]. It has been shown that PM2.5 is a public health concern whose exposure leads to decreased life expectancy [13–16]. The high concentration of CO forms carboxyhemoglobin (COHb) and exacerbates heart attack and also affects nervous system, NO₂ causes bronchitis and bronchopneumonia, and SO₂ causes eye irritation, shortness of breath, chronic bronchitis, asthma, various heart diseases, lung disease, cancer [11], and conjunctivitis [17]. O₃ is associated with stimulation of transcription factors and increased expression of cytokine and adhesion molecules which lead to the development of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases [18–20]. Air pollution's association with autoimmune diseases has been published [21, 22]. Air pollution has been emerging as a major threat to the whole ecosystem.

Till date, majority of studies on impacts of air pollution on human health have been done in North America and Europe. Only few studies on this regard have been done in region like Nepal. It has been found that, with high level of air pollution exposure, Nepal, especially Kathmandu, is suffering from a potentially serious human health burden from air pollution [21]. Air pollution has long been regarded as a silent killer responsible for causing a variety of chronic and infectious diseases. Globally, unhealthy environment causes a total of 12.6 million deaths [21] and air pollution is solely responsible for 7 million deaths annually [22]. Every year air pollution is linked with around 6.5 million premature deaths globally, of which household air pollution causes 3.5 million and ambient air pollution causes 3 million deaths and the future scenario by the 2040 is assumed to increase up to 7.5 million premature deaths per year [23]. PM2.5 caused an estimated 7.6% of total global mortality in 2015 and was the fifth-ranking global mortality risk factor. Although global rates of mortality due to PM2.5 exposure decreased from 1990 to 2015 as a result of improved air quality in high-income countries [24], In Nepal's case the impact on human health is equally severe. By 2030 annual premature deaths in Nepal, due to outdoor air pollution, are expected to be 24,000 [25]. In Nepal, the commonest diseases like respiratory illness, allergy, and eye infection and chronic diseases like lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), Ischaemic Heart Disease (IHD), and stroke are present in an alarming rate. Noncommunicable Diseases (NCDs) have been the major cause of human death accounting for 60% of deaths. Of NCDs cardiovascular diseases have caused a maximum death of 22% followed by chronic respiratory diseases 13%, cancer 8%, and other NCDs 14%. Premature (between ages of 30 and 70 years) mortality due to NCDs is 22% [21]. Data of Global Health Observatory (GHO) for mortality from ambient air pollution in Nepal in 2012 shows a threatening rate of 9,944 deaths of which Ischaemic Heart Disease (IHD) caused the highest death rate of 33.4% followed by stroke 32%, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) 17.8%, lung cancer 9.3%, and Acute Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (ALRTI) 7.4%. The number of female deaths was higher than that of male deaths in each disease [27]. Data of Department of Health (DoH) services in Nepal shows that, in 2013-2014, COPD was the most common cause of mortality among inpatients and respiratory tract diseases were the most common reason for outpatients' consultations with both upper and lower respiratory tract infections being within the top four [26].

In a hospital based study, NCD prevalence was 31% out of which COPD was 43%, cardiovascular disease was 40%, and cancer was 5% [27]. A study done in hospitalized patients of various hospitals of Kathmandu Valley shows a high prevalence of respiratory diseases. Among the diseases, COPD was the most prevalent one with a significant proportion of other diseases too. Gender-wise distribution showed that of total inpatients 51.3% were male and 48.7% were female. District-wise distribution showed that highest number of patients came from Kathmandu 44.4% followed by Lalitpur 10.3% and Bhaktapur 10.2%. Overall morbidity was 44.4% and the highest morbidity rate was seen in COPD [24]. A hospital based study outside Kathmandu Valley in Chitwan showed that 48.4% of COPD patients had a history of the disease since more than 5 years [28]. A study in 2017 has shown that 2.7–3.4 million preterm births might be associated with PM_{2.5} exposure in 2010 globally [29]. Nepal also has a significant number of preterm births of 14% [30]. No clear cut reasons have been found for this high preterm birth, but air pollution can arguably have an important impact on this. Air pollution is rising as an occupational hazard in Nepal, both in Kathmandu and in other cities like Pokhara, Nepalgunj especially in traffic police who are being continuously exposed to dusty roads [31, 32]. Due to this pulmonary functions have been significantly worsened in the traffic police working in Kathmandu [33]. Airborne occupational hazards are equally present in brick kiln workers and grocery workers in Kathmandu, whose health has been seriously hampered and needs quick action for protection [34, 35]. According to World Bank, air pollution stands as fourth major factor for causing death worldwide leaving metabolic risks, dietary risks, and tobacco smoking behind. Globally, 1 in 10 deaths is understood to be caused by air pollution [36]. Hazards due to air pollution have been a great economic burden too. A data on impact of air pollution on human health shows a global loss of \$225 billion annually of which South Asia has been the most severely affected region suffering a loss of more than \$66 billion alone annually, which is approximately 1% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) [37].

Research Methodology

The data and procedures employed to develop this study are described below.

Monthly data were considered and refer to January 2009 to December 2022, totaling 120 observations. Data on air pollutants were provided by the Environmental Company of Nepal. The atmospheric variables were selected by searching on Scopus, Web of Science, Lilacs, Medline, and Pubmed and selecting similar studies investigating which pollutants are related to disease mortality and air pollution. Mortality rate data were obtained from the Department of Informatics of the Nepal Health System and served as a basis for calculating mortality rates considering the size of the population. The diseases in the database are classified according to the 10th Revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is classified as ICD-10 codes J40 to J44 range: J40 (bronchitis not specified as acute or chronic), J41 (simple and mucopurulent chronic bronchitis), J42 (unspecified chronic bronchitis), J43 (emphysema) and J44 (other chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases). Lung cancer is classified as ICD-10 code C34 (malignant neoplasm of bronchus and lung). The following time series were considered for VAR modeling: particulate matter 10 (PM₁₀), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), COPD rate, and LC rate. The variables were obtained from the monthly average provided by Government of Nepal Ministry of Forests and Environment Department of Environment Air Quality Monitoring, and the COPD and LC rates were calculated according to Equations (1) and (2).

The methodology used to adjust the models was based on the VAR modeling to better understand the short-term interrelationships (12 periods) between the variables. After selecting the most appropriate VAR model, variance decomposition and impulse response function (IRF) analysis were performed to determine the dynamics between the time series (Hill et al., 2010; Sims, 1980). The steps required to develop the study are described in Fig. 1, and detailed description of the method can be consulted.

To adjust the VAR model, the stationarity condition of the series must first be verified by unit root tests because the stationary behavior is an assumption for the fit of the model and explain the short-term relationships. Then, the

influence of one variable on the other is analyzed using the Granger causality test. The block exogeneity test is also used to determine the degree of exogeneity of the variables that will be part of the model. After selecting the order of the variables to be part of the model and the number of lags required by the variables, the parameters are estimated using the maximum likelihood method. Then, variance decomposition and IRF analysis are used considering 12 months from that point onward in order to understand the dynamics between the variables.

The stability of the parameters estimated by the VAR model is ensured by assuming the stationary behavior of the variables. The following unit root tests were used: Augmented Dickey and Fuller (ADF) (Dickey and Fuller, 1981); Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS) (Kwiatkowski et al., 1992), and Phillips and Perron (PP) - (Phillips and Perron, 1988). The series were tested at level and in the first differences until the stationarity condition was reached.

The Granger causality test assumes that the model variables are stationary and based on identifying possible relationships between the variables that will be part of the model. If no causal relationship between one of the time series and the others is found (i.e., its coefficient value is approximately equal to 0), this variable should be removed from the model since it will make the model more restrained. The Granger causality test is important as it allows only the variables that present a causal relationship in the model (Granger, 1986).

The equation of the VAR model of order p is given as follows (Enders, 2014; Zhang et al., 2017):

$$y_t = C_i + A_1 y_{t-1} + A_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_{it}$$
 In Equation (3), C_i corresponds to the model constant, where i can assume values of 1, 2, ..., n . y_t is a vector of the n -dimensional variable. The autoregressive coefficients are given by A_s , where s assumes the values 1, 2, ..., p and i assumes the values 1, 2, ..., n . Finally, ε_{it} corresponds to white noise, where i assumes the values of 1, 2, ..., n . To determine the order (p) of the VAR model, three penalizing criteria were used: Akaike information criterion (AIC) (Akaike, 1974), Bayesian information criterion (BIC) (Schwarz, 1978), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ) (Hannan, E. J.; Quinn, 1979). By these penalizing criteria, it is possible to identify the best fit and number of lags. The following equations give the values calculated for the penalizing criteria. The model selected was the one that presented the lowest values for the penalizing criteria. According to Sobral and Barreto (2011), it is recommended to use the AIC criterion when the number of observations of the variables is low. Otherwise, the BIC criterion is more efficient. In addition to adjusting the VAR model, the dynamics between variables can be understood by applying a structural shock in the investigated time series.

The IRF analysis is used to characterize the dynamic structure existing between the VAR variables. The technique shows the behavior of the variables soon after applying an external shock to the exogenous variables. This external shock is performed in terms of standard deviations, that is, if the exogenous variable is modified by one standard deviation, the future behavior of the endogenous variable can be identified over time. Through the IRF, it is possible to check the time required for the endogenous variable to stabilize or return to its normal level after the shock (Brooks, 2014). When a shock is applied to one of the variables, the current and future effects are transmitted to all variables of interest in the model since all of the time series are interrelated. Sims (1980) proposed using a recursive system where some coefficients of the model assume a value equal to zero. The shocks are transmitted to the variables of interest through a triangular model of residual decomposition known as Cholesky decomposition (Higham, 1990), enabling the relationship between the variables to be investigated. Another commonly used technique with IRF is variance decomposition.

Another way to investigate the dynamics existing between VAR variables is by prediction error variance decomposition. In the same way as the IRF, variance decomposition allows the behavior of endogenous variables after structural shocks to be analyzed and the relative participation of each shock on the variables to be measured. Moreover, the percentage of prediction error arising from endogenous variables during a given period is presented (Bueno, 2012); hence, variance decomposition allows the model results and percentages of the predicting error from the endogenous variables to be verified (de Senna and Souza, 2016). Therefore, the short-term interrelationship of mortality rates by COPD and LC due to air pollutants were identified.

Table 1

Variables	Weight unit	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation	Relative Standard Deviation (%)
PM ₁₀	µg/m ³	33.20	31.34	16.53	62.61	9.46	28.49
O ₃	µg/m ³	37.21	36.51	19.84	59.83	8.86	23.80
CO	mg/m ³	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	29.30
NO ₂	µg/m ³	29.30	28.70	15.40	45.00	5.86	20.02
SO ₂	µg/m ³	6.59	6.20	2.93	12.9	2.24	34.10
COPD	*	2.15	2.02	1.37	4.12	0.57	27.50
LC	*	2.33	2.04	0.95	4.51	1.23	52.80

The represented variables are particulate matter 10 (PM10), ozone (O3), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO2), sulfur dioxide (SO2), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and lung cancer (LC). *Mortality rates from COPD and LC per 100,000 population.

Results and discussion

In this study, pollutants associated with pulmonary diseases were analyzed. The main results of the descriptive statistical

analysis of the pollutants PM10, O3, CO, NO2, SO2, COPD, and LC are shown in Table 1.

The highest mortality rate by month occurred in July (2009-2022), being 4.12 per 100,000 population (1700,00 deaths) for COPD and 4.51 per 100,000 population (1861,00 deaths) for LC. Santos Gomes et al. (2018) and Esquivel et al. (2011) also noted a high mortality rate in the winter period (June to September), which is likely due to low precipitation, relative humidity variations, and mild temperatures. Furthermore, the most frequently found pollutants in this winter period were PM10 and NO2 (Martins et al.,2017). The factors that most likely influence the high concentrations of these pollutants in the atmosphere include vehicle emissions, industrial areas, and population growth, especially in the metropolitan region of Nepal. Cardoso et al. (2019) reported that PM10

Fig. 1. Chart of pollutants and pulmonary diseases

Table 2

Granger Causation	F-statistic	p-value (<0.05)
PM₁₀ ↔ O₃	45.55	<0.01
O₃ ↔ NO₂	41.25	<0.01
SO₂ ↔ O₃	19.13	<0.01
O₃ ↔ Δ(CO)	18.22	<0.01
NO₂ ↔ Δ(CO)	13.26	<0.01
PM₁₀ ↔ Δ(CO)	12.39	<0.01
SO₂ ↔ PM₁₀	8.34	<0.01
O₃ → COPD	8.29	<0.01
NO₂ ↔ SO₂	7.64	<0.01
NO₂ → PM₁₀	6.79	<0.01
PM₁₀ → Δ(LC)	5.07	0.01
Δ(CO) → SO₂	4.93	0.01
PM₁₀ → COPD	4.83	0.01
NO₂ → COPD	4.49	0.01
COPD → Δ(LC)	3.30	0.04

The→symbol indicates unidirectional causality; TheΔsymbol indicates bidirectional causality. H0: series “X” does not cause series “Y” in the direction of Granger; H1: series “X” causes series “Y” in the direction of Granger; a ¼ 0.05.

Emissions associated with urbanization and living near industrial areas are risk factors for people with LC. In another study,

geographic location, socioeconomic status, residential mobility, and long-term exposure to PM_{2,5} and O₃ were associated with increased mortality from LC and COPD (Cakmak et al., 2018). After characterizing the sample using central tendency and dispersion measures, the time series were visually inspected (Fig. 1). Starting in January 2014, the mortality rate of LC began to rise (Fig. 1), while CO, SO₂ and NO₂ began to decrease. The implementation of emission control programs directly affected the substantial reduction in pollutant concentrations. In S~ao Paulo State, State Decree no. 59113/2013, which took effect in 2013, required that air quality management be carried out through Air Quality Standards and be based on the guidelines established by the WHO (Environmental Company of the State of S~ao Paulo, 2020). However, Santana et al. (2020) reported that despite the decreased concentrations of CO, SO₂, and NO₂ in S~ao Paulo, these pollutants showed a positive correlation with hospitalizations for respiratory diseases. In addition, there is a time lag between exposure to the pollutant, the development of diseases and the resulting mortality (Machin and Nascimento, 2018). It is necessary to highlight that LC mortality rate increased sharply in the first semester of 2014 (Fig. 2). In 2014, Brazil faced an intense economic crisis that compromised the Unified Health System (Martins et al., 2019), and the increased number of deaths from LC in this period may be associated with a lack of prevention and failures in treating the disease, in the city of S~ao Paulo (Pujol et al., 2018; Zavarez et al., 2020). However, according to Belloni et al. (2020), cancers are chronic and multifactorial diseases resulting from genetic, environmental, and behavioral influence. Hence, individual risk factors may also have contributed, such as smoking (Wang et al., 2020; Wünsch Filho et al., 2010), heavy alcohol consumption (Chao et al., 2011; Latino-Martel et al., 2016), and underlying diseases (He et al., 2017; Shen et al., 2016). This article only aimed to investigate the effects of air pollutants on mortality rates from COPD and LC.

The time series that were visually stationary at level were PM₁₀, O₃, NO₂, SO₂, COPD, while CO and LC were non-stationary. To

confirm these results, the unit root tests ADF, PP, and KPSS were applied. The results indicated that PM₁₀, O₃, CO,NO₂, SO₂ and COPD (p < 0.05) were stationary at level. The series in first differences (D) were CO and LC, represented by D(CO) and D(LC), and the test results. To identify the causal relationships of the variables, the Granger causality test was applied. Table 2 shows the unidirectional relationships (5% significance level) between O₃ and COPD, NO₂ and PM₁₀, PM₁₀ and D(LC), D(CO) and SO₂, PM₁₀ and COPD, NO₂ and COPD and COPD and D(LC). The other causal relationships are bidirectional with the same level of significance. The test result allows all variables to be used in the VAR model. The VAR modeling begins by verifying the lag order number using the Lag Order Selection Criteria Test

and AIC, BIC, and HQ criteria. The result of one lag, VAR (1), was chosen, where all pollutants have a lasting effect of one month, that is, the previous month influences the current one. The results obtained for the penalizing criteria considered are presented. The Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald test indicates the order of

Table 3

The variable order in Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald test.

Variables	Chi-Square (χ^2)	p-value
O₃	97.28	<0.01
Δ(CO)	18.06	<0.01
COPD	10.52	<0.01
PM₁₀	8.85	<0.01
NO₂	7.73	0.01
Δ(LC)	5.10	0.02
SO₂	5.08	0.02

variables according to exogeneity (Table 3). The variable O₃ had the highest c₂ (97.28), while D(LC) had the lowest c₂ (5.08). Following the criterion of the most exogenous to the least, the order of the variables is O₃, D(CO), COPD, PM₁₀, NO₂, D(LC) and SO₂. The VAR model with the adjusted coefficients, assuming the stationarity criterion.

The IRF analysis was performed via graphical representation and VAR modeling. The time series related to COPD and D(LC) received an impact through the series: particulate matter 10 (PM₁₀), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide D(CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and sulfur dioxide (SO₂). The results obtained after an external shock in terms of two standard deviation. The variations caused by the shock in the variable O₃ created a negative response in COPD; in the eighth period, which is stabilized. The response of COPD related to the impulse in O₃ has the most significant variation among all pollutants. Arbex and Conceic (2001) investigated the relationship between emergency room visits for patients with COPD and the concentration of some air pollutants in Nepal and found an association of NO₂ and O₃ with patients with COPD. The analysis exposed that the people who are affected by these pollutants are mostly women and the elderly. The variable D(CO) causes an initial variation in COPD characterized by a decrease that is stabilized in period nine. This pollutant significantly influences people living in urban centers and is primarily caused by heavy traffic, thus increasing exposure of the local population to it (Cançado et al., 2006), which is associated with respiratory and cardiovascular diseases such as COPD (Wang et al., 2019). The variable PM₁₀ first causes a decrease in COPD, followed by an increase in the seventh period that remains for the following periods. According to Pothirat et al. (2019), short-term exposure to PM₁₀ affects the quality of life of patients with COPD, in addition to possibly impairing the respiratory and cardiovascular system. In cases involving children and the elderly, the consequences are even more severe as these individuals are more vulnerable (Matus and Oyarzún, 2019; Weichenthal et al., 2014). The increased levels of exposure to particulate matter in Nepal were associated with

increased hospitalizations for COPD in the elderly (Gouveia et al., 2006). Shocks in the variables NO₂ and D(LC) cause few oscillations in COPD, which stabilizes in the ninth and twelfth period, respectively. When inhaled by humans, NO₂ can cause lung problems (Amaducci and Downs, 2020). However, in this study, NO₂ was not the main pollutant responsible for increasing the mortality rate due to COPD and LC. The SO₂ variable initially causes variations of growth and decline in COPD; in the ninth period, it is characterized by a negative decrease that is not stable. This pollutant is responsible for causing photochemical fog in the atmosphere and also extremely harmful to human health. The consequences of SO₂ exposure are respiratory diseases, COPD, difficulty in breathing, and premature death (Khaniabadi et al., 2017). Gouveia et al. (2006) also conducted research in the city of nepalgunj and noted that pollutants PM₁₀, O₃, CO, NO₂, and SO₂ are significantly associated with hospitalizations for COPD. The variations caused by the shock in the variable O₃ create an initially negative response in D(LC), which in the second period is characterized by an increase; in period nine, the variations are stabilized. Among all pollutants, O₃ is responsible for the most significant

short-term variations in the diseases studied. A study conducted in several Chinese cities found a short-term association between O₃ and LC and revealed that the consequences of exposure to this pollutant may be exacerbated in hot seasons(Wang et al., 2019a). In S~ao Paulo, O₃ was associated with infantile respiratory morbidity in hot periods (Gonçalves et al., 2005).

Table 4

Period	O ₃	Δ (CO)	COPD	PM ₁₀	NO ₂	Δ (LC)	SO ₂
Variance decomposition of COPD							
1	4.00	8.77	87.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	12.61	10.24	76.80	0.22	0.04	0.01	0.09
3	18.63	10.56	69.57	0.71	0.03	0.06	0.43
4	21.74	10.30	65.28	1.57	0.07	0.08	0.96
5	22.58	9.93	63.12	2.69	0.16	0.07	1.46
6	22.25	9.59	62.27	3.83	0.23	0.07	1.76
7	21.61	9.33	62.09	4.74	0.28	0.10	1.86
8	21.09	9.15	62.18	5.31	0.29	0.13	1.84
9	20.75	9.03	62.37	5.59	0.29	0.16	1.81
10	20.51	8.95	62.58	5.68	0.29	0.18	1.82
11	20.32	8.91	62.77	5.68	0.28	0.19	1.84
12	20.19	8.89	62.92	5.66	0.28	0.19	1.87
Variance decomposition of Δ(LC)							
1	0.23	0.06	28.30	2.00	2.97	66.43	0.00
2	2.28	0.27	28.53	2.07	4.11	62.70	0.04
3	2.28	0.31	28.56	2.31	4.14	62.32	0.08
4	2.72	0.58	28.48	2.45	4.14	61.55	0.08
5	3.64	0.73	28.25	2.45	4.08	60.73	0.13
6	4.42	0.82	28.00	2.43	4.04	60.72	0.26
7	4.81	0.85	27.83	2.46	4.02	59.61	0.43
8	4.90	0.85	27.74	2.54	4.03	59.40	0.56
9	4.89	0.85	27.70	2.64	4.03	59.28	0.63
10	4.90	0.85	27.70	2.69	4.03	59.22	0.65
11	4.95	0.85	27.70	2.72	4.03	59.16	0.65
12	5.00	0.85	27.64	2.72	4.02	59.12	0.65

Conclusion

The study has some limitations, including the autoregressive vector method, which allows short-term analysis. For long-term application using the vector error correction (VEC) model, the variables must be cointegrated, which was not the case for the present study. The database of air pollutants collected at Government of Nepal Ministry of Forests and Environment Department of Environment Air Quality Monitoring is one of the limitations, as they have some gaps in their measurements, especially in daily data. Therefore, we opted to use monthly data. Nonetheless, individual risk factors such as smoking, heavy consumption of alcohol, and underlying diseases were not considered in this study. This is the first application to examine the interrelationship between these variables in Nepal using VAR modeling. The autoregressive vector model was able to identify the air pollutants that have the most significant impact on diseases and enabled the understanding of the interrelationship between the variables investigated by the variance decomposition. The variables that had the most significant impact on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease mortality rate and lung cancer mortality rate in the analyzed period were O₃ and NO₂. This indicates that these pollutants have more influence on people’s health and the development of lung diseases. The proposed method can significantly contribute to the short-term monitoring of mortality rates of diseases caused by air pollutant intervention, thus preventing the development of diseases and increasing mortality statistics from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and lung cancer.

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